

ANALYZING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STAKE HOLDER MANAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN BANK DHOFAR

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7584842>

Published Date: 30-January-2023

Abstract: The carrying of business activities results in the development of relationships with stakeholders. The stakeholders are the consumers, employees, investors, and suppliers. Hence, the stakeholders are the individuals with which the business encounters in many forms. CSR is a complicated and multidimensional organizational phenomenon understood to be the scope for how an organization is consciously responsible for its actions and non-actions and their impact on its stakeholders; hence, organizational performance directly influences its stakeholders (Jamil & Al-Aina, 2017). The research problem is to investigate whether the Bank Dhofar manages its stakeholder and considers their inputs in decision-making. The general purpose of the research is the elaboration of stakeholders' and organizational performance. The quantitative research design is used for the analysis of the relationship between stakeholder management and the organizational performance of Bank Dhofar. The Pearson correlation of the independent variable (stakeholders' management) with the dependent variable (organizational performance) is 0.441. The correlation of 0.4112 emphasizes a strong positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The R square change is .195; this depicts that the independent variable (Stakeholders' management) changes the organizational performance by 19%. The minimum significant value of Cronbach's Alpha is 0.5; hence the Cronbach's Alpha rate of this research study is 0.710, which means the variables of this study are measured reliably in questionnaire responses. The valid percentile is 74; the rate tells us about the validity of the questionnaire and questions asked by participants. Hence, the researchers can rely on the study and its questionnaires because of high-reliability statistics. There is the suggestion for banking sector and organizations that they should develop a plan to enhance employees' input in organizational decision-making. Bank Dhofar can help onboard its employees and their input through various methods such as the inauguration of performance evaluation programs, circulating questionnaires, or developing a direct communication mechanism with executive members of the organization. The banks must allow and enhance the cooperation with the state's financial and legislation institutions by following the central bank or capital market guidelines and giving the Bank's input in financial decisions of the banking sector.

Keywords: stakeholders, consumers, employees, investors, banking sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Organizations with the motive of profitable operations are involved in business activities. The organizational activities enable the entity's performance in the form of financial performance, market performance, and stakeholders' value. The carrying of business activities results in the development of relationships with stakeholders. The stakeholders are the consumers, employees, investors, and suppliers. Hence, the stakeholders are the individuals with which the business encounters in many forms. CSR is a complicated and multidimensional organizational phenomenon understood to be the scope for how an organization is consciously responsible for its actions and non-actions and their impact on its stakeholders;

hence, organizational performance directly influences its stakeholders (Jamil & Al-Aina, 2017). The behavioral journal report also emphasizes the impact of regulators on organizational performance due to abiding by and monitoring statutory rules (Jade & Phines, 2019).

The stakeholders' management is a vital and critical component of strategic management in the operational efficiencies of a company. Competent strategic management helps a company keep its social license to operate, becoming a more critical business factor in a world where different stakeholders are becoming more aware of business issues. Recently, consumers have become more aware of ethics and the environment and are more interested in a company's products and actions. For a company to be successful in the long run, strategic management must be based on these criteria (Rawashdeh, 2017). Stakeholder management is one of the management fields that is growing the fastest. Stakeholder management programs say that companies should try to reach the same goals as their stakeholders. A stakeholder is a term for a group of personal traits that make it easier to learn quickly.

This research aims to elaborate on all the stakeholders and their impact on banking performance. Bank Dhofar is the organization for which the stakeholders' analysis will be carried out. The Bank Dhofar's performance is evaluated by studying the stakeholders' management – customers, employees, peer banks, and regulators. Customers are the critical component of Bank Dhofar's performance, as these are the target audience for successful operations. The employees are also key stakeholders, as they directly interact with customers and perform organizational duties. Each segment of stakeholders at some level contributes to the operational success of a banking institution. Customers are key stakeholders as they are the direct beneficiary of banking services. The employees are the frontline participants for smooth operations. Investors influence financial and investment decisions. The financial authorities, such as the central Bank or capital market authority of Oman, governs the banking and legal policies. This research focuses on organizational performance influenced by its managing stakeholders.

1.2. Statement of the Research Problem:

The stakeholders are active participants in the operational success of a banking institution. The research problem is to investigate whether the Bank Dhofar manages its stakeholder and considers their inputs in decision-making.

1.3 Aim of the study:

1.3.1 Aim:

This research project aims to evaluate the impact of stakeholders on organizational performance. As discussed, organizational performance is compared with the actual and intended performance. The Bank Dhofar's performance is evaluated by studying the stakeholders' management-customers, employees, peer banks, and regulators.

1.3.2 Objectives of the Research:

The following are the crucial objectives of the research:

1. To analyze the relationship between stakeholder management and organizational performance in Bank Dhofar.
2. To examine the impacts of stakeholder management on organizational performance in Bank Dhofar.
3. To evaluate the stakeholder management process.
4. To analyze the challenges of stakeholder management.

1.4. Research Questions:

1. What is the relationship between stakeholder management and organizational performance in Bank Dhofar?
2. What are the impacts of stakeholder management on organizational performance in Bank Dhofar?
3. What is the stakeholder management process?
4. What are the challenges of stakeholder management?

1.5. Significance of the study:

Although the previous research on Oman's banking sector emphasizes the importance of customer service relationship management, customers are one of the stakeholders. This research aims to elaborate on all the stakeholders and their impact on banking performance. The successful completion of this research project would highlight the relationship between

stakeholder management and organizational performance in the banking sector. The literature and stakeholders' responses in this research would help the banking institutions develop a plan that enhances employees' input in organizational decision-making. Bank Dhofar can help onboard its employees and their input through various methods such as the inauguration of performance evaluation programs, circulating questionnaires, or developing a direct communication mechanism with executive members of the organization. The research highlight the importance of allowing and enhancing cooperation with the state's financial and legislative institutions by following the central bank or capital market guidelines and giving the Bank's input in financial decisions of the banking sector. The study will help banks to create a practical, diverse, competitive, and innovative environment for stakeholders.

1.6. Scope of the study:

The general purpose of the research is the elaboration of stakeholders' and organizational performance. The research will evaluate the impact of stakeholders on organizational performance. The essential characteristic of the research population is that it is related to Bank Dhofar and engages with Bank. The population of the study is the stakeholders (consumers, suppliers, employees, capital market investors, and authorities) of Bank Dhofar. The sample size comprises 100 individuals acting as stakeholders in Bank Dhofar. The sampling technique is random, as the questionnaires and surveys will be circulated to the population for detailed responses. The vital benefit of the simple random sampling technique is that there is a lack of bias because every participant is chosen randomly. The duration for the research is three months for theoretical analysis and two weeks for a survey into the inter-city of Oman- Seeb, and Salalah. The quantitative research design will be used for the analysis of the relationship between stakeholder management and the organizational performance of Bank Dhofar. The research design for this study is correlational and descriptive. The questionnaire will be circulated in a sample size. The responses gathered from participants will be tested and analyzed in SPSS for correlational analysis. The descriptive research design for the study is analyzing the existing literature and research articles related to stakeholders, organizational performance, and bank Dhofar.

1.7. Limitation of the study:

- I. **Biasness-** There is a high probability of biased responses by customers and employees.
- II. **Corporate policy secrecy-** The corporate and banking policy may not represent the on-ground situation of stakeholders' management due to secrecy policies.
- III. **Lack of resources-** The reach to officials and executive board members of Bank Dhofar could not become possible due to a lack of sources for contacts and restrictions by the Bank's information department due to legality issues
- IV. **Responding of officials-** The Central Bank of Oman and Capital Market officials did not respond. They were the key stakeholders that legally defined the Bank's status and performance in the banking sector.
- V. **Limited analysis-** The critical limitation of the research is limited analysis due to less sample size and accessibility to stakeholders.

1.8. Operational Definition of Terms:

- **Stakeholders' management:** Managing the participants of banking operations such as customers, employees, central bank, executive director team, and financing authorities.
- **Organizational performance:** The operational, legal, financial, or strategic performance
- **Central Bank:** The Central Bank of the Sultanate of Oman regulates banking institutions.
- **Financial authorities:** Capital market, Omani investment fund authority, Central Bank, and institutions.

1.9. Structure of the study:

The research structure comprises an introduction, literature review, methodology, data analysis, conclusion, and recommendations.

1.10. Overview of chapters:

The organizational activities enable the entity's performance in the form of financial performance, market performance, and stakeholders' value. The carrying of business activities results in the development of relationships with stakeholders. The stakeholders are the consumers, employees, investors, and suppliers. Chapter one of the research elaborated on the research

problem of analyzing the relationship between stakeholders' management and organizational performance. The above part also emphasized the significance of the study and research questions. Chapter two of the research will shed light on existing literature on stakeholder management and its impact on Bank Dhofar's performance. The next chapter of the research study elaborates and emphasizes the literature review, with critical evaluation and a comprehensive summary of the organizational performance concerning stakeholders. The research methodology section will overview the data analysis method used to get the quantitative results. Similarly, chapter 4 will be comprised of statistical data gathered through a questionnaire survey and analysis in SPSS. The last chapter will list the recommendations, issues faced in the research, and the conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction:

Organizations with the motive of profitable operations are involved in business activities. The organizational activities enable the entity's performance in the form of financial performance, market performance, and stakeholders' value. The carrying of business activities results in the development of relationships with stakeholders. Stakeholder management is an evolving process that helps an organization bring on new workers, get the most out of them, keep the ones they already have, and hire well-qualified applicants. Stakeholders are there when there is a strong desire to improve the way something works. It can only live with an investigation that is done on purpose. Ecological economics magazine concludes with the correlation analysis that stakeholders have a mediation role in the organizational performance of a firm. Since it started in the 1990s, stakeholder management has become more critical as more businesses realize how critical employee skills are to getting results. Interest in research on stakeholder management has grown. Since conference presentations and symposia were included in the study, more authors and research departments from all over the world were found to be involved in stakeholder management.

2.2. Stakeholder management:

(Adnan, 2017) states that stakeholder management is the process of identifying, organizing, communicating, and aligning the perspective of those who influence the organization in any way with the organizational strategy. The carrying of business activities results in the development of relationships with stakeholders. The stakeholders are the consumers, employees, investors, and suppliers. Hence, the stakeholders are the individuals with which the business encounters in many forms.

Stakeholder management is an evolving process that helps an organization bring on new workers, get the most out of them, keep the ones they already have, and hire well-qualified applicants. Stakeholders are there when there is a strong desire to improve the way something works. It can only live with an investigation that is done on purpose. Because one's ability to change and grow is more evident during this phase, stakeholders often don't show up until after some practice. A stakeholder is more than just a person's "basic" ability to do a task. It's often the result of learning and doing things from a young age. Stakeholder management uses strategic human resource planning to make businesses and organizations more valuable and help them reach their goals. Strategic management is essential for a business to be successful in the long run (Adnan, 2017). Strategic management of a company or business unit involves developing a business strategy with clear goals, making plans for reaching those goals, coordinating daily activities to help reach those goals, and allocating the resources needed to reach those goals.

2.3. Organizational performance:

Organizational performance refers to an organization's output with its measurement against the input. The term "output" here implies the actual organizational performance in the form of financial, market, and shareholder value performance. Similarly, the term "input" aligns with the concept of strategies and resources utilized by an organization. The critical outcomes of organizational performance are the following:

2.4. Relationship between stakeholder management and organizational performance:

As discussed above, the significant actors that participate in an organization's operational efficiencies are customers, investors, suppliers, and employees. The employees are one of the most critical stakeholders that play an influential role in an organization to align the business strategies and achieve goals. Since it started in the 1990s, stakeholder management has become more critical as more businesses realize how critical employee skills are to getting results. Interest in research on stakeholder management has grown. Since conference presentations and symposia were included in the study, more authors and research departments from all over the world were found to be involved in stakeholder management. Businesses need human resources to develop, innovate, and be creative to grow and maintain a competitive advantage. To improve its creative skills, the company must teach its employees how to work creatively and interact with customers regularly. (Marmenout, 2018) talk about how talented Middle Eastern women are but how they can't use their skills on the job. The

study was mostly about women who work in Oman (Farndale, 2017). The study's results include information about the environment and how Omani women's stakeholder development has helped them improve at their jobs and learn new skills. (Sanyal, 2018) says that training and development courses in the banking industry help workers do their jobs better. They looked at the training and performance of 300 bank workers to find a statistically significant link between the two. They used statistical methods: ANOVA, Pearson correlation, and regression analysis. The research found that the training and development programs at the selected banks made their employees more productive and that training and development significantly affected how well employees did their jobs. Research on stakeholder management is organized by their works using stakeholder theories and a value hypothesis (Gallardo-Gallardo, 2016).

2.5. Impact of stakeholder management on organizational performance:

Keeping the objective in view, the research report named "Banking sector in Oman: strategic issues, challenges and future scenarios," published by the deans of different business colleges in Oman, elaborates the CSR in respect of the impact on bank stakeholders. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a complicated and multidimensional organizational phenomenon that is understood to be the scope for how an organization is consciously responsible for its actions and non-actions and their impact on its stakeholders; hence, the organizational performance directly influences its stakeholders (Jamil & Al-Aina, 2017). The report also emphasizes the impact of regulators on organizational performance due to abiding by and monitoring statutory rules.

The Electronic Journal of Business Ethics and Organization Studies published focuses on the resources affecting the Bank's CSR activities based on stakeholders' perceptions. The results from this study helped researchers and firms by providing proper direction in formulating the CSR strategy and policy. It is also expected to identify the dominant variables that profoundly affect CSR pursuits. This research provides a comprehensive evaluation of resources required from a broad base of stakeholders.

2.6 Stakeholder management process:

Competent strategic management helps a company keep its social license to operate, becoming a more critical business factor in a world where different stakeholders are becoming more aware of business issues. Recently, consumers have become more aware of ethics and the environment and are more interested in a company's products and actions. For a company to be successful in the long run, strategic management must be based on these criteria (Rawashdeh, 2017). Stakeholder management is one of the management fields that is growing the fastest. Stakeholder management programs say that companies should try to reach the same goals as their stakeholders. A stakeholder is a term for a group of personal traits that make it easier to learn quickly. People with these traits may move up faster than their peers with the same skill, athleticism, and talent. A stakeholder is a person's ability to learn their trade and move up in it (Altınöz, 2015). Businesses need human resources to develop, innovate, and be creative to grow and maintain a competitive advantage. To improve its creative skills, the company must teach its employees how to work creatively and interact with customers regularly.

2.7 Challenges of stakeholder management:

The article talks about the idea of architectures for managing stakeholders. Then, the human capital theory's inadequacies are examined by analyzing four stakeholder management ideologies and how they make different claims about the importance of different stakeholders and stakeholder management systems. After explaining the details of the things being looked at, a value judgment is made. It sets up a structure using four activities that create value (value creation, value capture, value leverage, and value protection). This approach looks at non-HR literature on value creation, the RBV viewpoint, dynamic capacities, and global knowledge management, among other things. Over the last 20 years, it has become more critical for multinational companies to stay competitive in the global market. The author stresses how important it is that this requirement is met to get people interested in stakeholder management again. In the late 1990s, the challenge of "global stakeholder management" pushed people to make this option possible. The authors then talk about the pros and cons of managing stakeholder engagement on a global scale. According to a study (Kolluru, 2016), how the staff interacts with the customer is a good indicator of how happy or unhappy the customer is with the banking industry. Her research continues to show how important people are to make a company more competitive. Organizations need to hire, train, and develop people to improve performance and production to meet their goals (Kolluru, 2016).

Changes to how decisions were made let people set up a business and banking system that helps the community (honesty, trust, harmony, equality, and consensus). Also, servant leadership grew, focusing on helping people reach the goals of an organization (Kronz, 2018). Individualism in the workforce and among executives was replaced by support for a corporate culture centered on achieving the most important goals. After this, the financial system switched to a systemic-drive organizational structure (Yellow), emphasizing insights, long-term thinking, and building a network-based organizational

structure with a common goal. Better decision-making processes allowed for balance from top to bottom and bottom to top, as well as connected leadership based on a long-term, visionary plan. This increased the value for everyone involved. Lastly, Oman's economic system is moving toward turquoise, which is a trend around the world (Marmenout, 2018). Because Oman has a vast population and a lot of competition, banks like Bank Dhofar have realized that if they want to do well, they need to work together to find solutions to the complicated global problems that plague the financial sector. Leaders at Bank Dhofar can spot trends in the banking industry, which lets them find new ways for the sector to grow. For example, the company grew its market share by buying the National Bank of Oman in 2018.

2.8. Theories of stakeholder management:

The three critical and well-known stakeholder management theories are agency, survival, and resource-based. The agency theory states that the organization and its employees play the agency role on the part of investors and shareholders. The theory suggests that there should be healthy relations with shareholders, and their perspective should align with the objectives of the business. The survival theory states that an organization should align with the external environment irrespective of shareholders' perspective. However, the theory emphasizes that businesses should consider external stakeholders. The resource-based theory states that entities should prefer internal factors such as employees. Applying any one theory from the above specified, it is evident that stakeholders have a role in organizational success.

2.9. Summary:

The carrying of business activities results in the development of relationships with stakeholders. The stakeholders are the consumers, employees, investors, and suppliers. Hence, the stakeholders are the individuals with which the business encounters in many forms. The organizational activities enable the entity's performance in the form of financial performance, market performance, and stakeholders' value. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a complicated and multidimensional organizational phenomenon understood to be the scope for how an organization is consciously responsible for its actions and non-actions and their impact on its stakeholders; hence, organizational performance directly influences its stakeholders. The report also emphasizes the impact of regulators on organizational performance due to abiding by and monitoring statutory rules. There are various theories that elaborate the stakeholder management process. The theory suggests that there should be healthy relations with shareholders, and their perspective should align with the objectives of the business. The survival theory states that an organization should align with the external environment irrespective of shareholders' perspective. However, the theory emphasizes that businesses should consider external stakeholders. The resource-based theory states that entities should prefer internal factors such as employees. Applying any one theory from the above specified, it is evident that stakeholders have a role in organizational success.

The literature review section emphasizes on challenges of stakeholder management. Over the last 20 years, it has become more critical for multinational companies to stay competitive in the global market. The author stresses how important it is that this requirement is met to get people interested in stakeholder management again. In the late 1990s, the challenge of "global stakeholder management" pushed people to make this option possible. The authors then talk about the pros and cons of managing stakeholder engagement on a global scale. According to a study (Kolluru, 2016), how the staff interacts with the customer is a good indicator of how happy or unhappy the customer is with the banking industry. Her research continues to show how important people are to make a company more competitive. Organizations need to hire, train, and develop people to improve performance and production to meet their goals (Kolluru, 2016).

3. RESEARCH METHHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction:

The research methodology chapter aims to elaborate the research design and statistical tool used for testing the responses of research participants. This section will also critically analyze the relationship between stakeholder management and the organizational performance of Bank Dhofar through focusing on research methodology such as population, sample size, design and tool of research. There will be the study and elaborate on the research design and quantitative analysis. The additional content in this chapter will identify the population and sample size used for the questionnaire and data analysis in SPSS.

3.2. Research Design

The quantitative research design will be used for the analysis of the relationship between stakeholder management and the organizational performance of Bank Dhofar. The research design for this study is correlational and descriptive. The

questionnaire will be circulated in a sample size. The responses gathered from participants will be tested and analyzed in SPSS for correlational analysis. The descriptive research design for the study is analyzing the existing literature and research articles related to stakeholders, organizational performance, and bank Dhofar.

3.3. Population of the study:

The population of the research is stakeholders. As described in chapter one, the stakeholders are clients, investors, employees, central bank employees, and associates related to authoritative institutions such as CPA, legislative bodies, etc., of the Sultanate of Oman. The essential characteristic of the research population is that it is related to Bank Dhofar and engages with Bank. The research population is categorized as employees, customers, investors, and central bank authorities. The population size cannot be measured accurately as a considerable number of employees in Bank Dhofar Central Bank of Oman. The total number of customers and details of Bank Dhofar's investors cannot be efficiently gathered. However, based on web material, annual reports, and Bank Dhofar's website, the number of employees is around 1,450.

3.4. Sampling Technique and Sampling Size:

The sample size is comprised of 100 respondents. The sampling technique is random, as the questionnaires and surveys will be circulated to the population for detailed responses. The vital benefit of the simple random sampling technique is that there is a lack of bias because every participant is chosen randomly. Every participant has an equal probability of being selected. It also requires minimum knowledge for a population study group.

3.5. Research Instruments and Validity and Reliability Testing:

The data collection tool used for the research respondents and sample size is a questionnaire. The questionnaires would be circulated to the population using online communication tools such as emails and personalized chat sources. The key benefit of using a questionnaire is that it saves costs. The responses can be delivered and then collected quickly time. The respondent's anonymity is also a critical concern that questionnaires maintain efficiently. There are bright chances of data accuracy.

The fixed surveys with a five Likert scale from strongly agree to disagree strongly. The survey questions will be considered the primary data, entered into comprehensive statistical analysis software SPSS. The data will then be tested with SPSS components such as frequency, a valid percent, and cumulative percent. The reliability and validity testing would be done through correlations, regressions, and outcome variables.

3.6. Data Collection Techniques:

The primary source of data collection technique is the circulation of questionnaires as a survey to the population. The questionnaire is a primary source of data collection and enables a high level of objectivity. The data becomes concrete as it involves numbers and variables. A literature review is the secondary data collection method for critically evaluating the research topic. The secondary data sources are existing literature, research material, and official banking articles with high credibility. Primary data collection techniques' key benefits are a high accuracy, up-to-date information, and better interpretation of data and research problems. The secondary data is less biased and easy to access compared to primary data, which is a statistical analysis based on questionnaire responses (Altınöz, 2015).

3.7. Data Analysis Technique:

The data analysis techniques for sample responses and research questions are regression, correlational, and reliability. This SPSS technique for regression, correlational, and reliability analysis provides concrete and fast answers. The relevancy and relationship between variables can be analyzed efficiently using regression and correlational techniques. The primary data will be entered into the comprehensive statistical analysis software SPSS. The key reason for Choosing the SPSS for data analysis is that it involves reliable data management, fast response, and accurate numerical analysis.

3.8. Legal, Ethical, and Social Considerations:

A. Ethical- The key ethical consideration of the research is to maintain the privacy and consent of participants in the research questionnaire response.

B. Social- The social considerations are maintaining dignity and respect and safeguarding respondents' interests.

C. Legal- The legal consideration is that participants should know the research purpose and objectives (Kolluru, 2016).

3.9. Summary:

The research methodology chapter emphasizes the research design, population, sampling and data collection technique, and critical ethical considerations. The sample size is comprised of 70 respondents. The sampling technique is random, as the questionnaires and surveys will be circulated to the population for detailed responses. The questionnaire is a primary source of data collection and enables a high level of objectivity. The data becomes concrete as it involves numbers and variables. A literature review is the secondary data collection method for critically evaluating the research topic. The data analysis techniques for sample responses and research questions are regression, correlational, and reliability. This SPSS technique for regression, correlational, and reliability analysis provides concrete and fast answers. The next chapter will present the data analysis and numeric value of questionnaire responses. The ethical, social and legal issues are maintaining the privacy & consent of participants in the research questionnaire response, maintaining dignity, respect & safeguarding respondents' interests, elaborating the research purpose and objectives to participants. The result of validity and reliability testing using SPSS will be listed in the last part of chapter four.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. Participants statistics:

Table 4.1.1

		What is your Gender	In which age bracket do you fall?	What is your current academic qualification?	How long have you been associated with Bank Dhofar?
N	Valid	74	74	74	74
	Missing	0	0	0	0
	41-50	33	44.6	44.6	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	100.0	

4.2. Frequency Table

Table 4.2.1: What is your Gender?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	45	60.8	60.8	60.8
	Female	29	39.2	39.2	100.0
	Total	74	100.0	100.0	

4.3. Table Correlations:

The correlation defines the relationship between two variables that either the variables have any significance with each other. For instance, does a change in one variable impact the other variable or not? If there is no effect, then there is 0 correlation. The correlation effect has two types- positive or negative. The two variables are the dependent and independent variables. If the change (increase) in the independent variable results decrease in the dependent variable, then there is a negative effect. Contrary to this, if the change (increase) in the independent variable results increase in the dependent variable, then there is a positive effect.

Table 4.3.1 Significance of correlation

		Stakeholders Management	Organizational Performance
Stakeholders Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.441**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	74	74
Organizational Performance	Pearson Correlation	.441**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	74	74

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The significance of correlation depicts the level of relationship between dependent and independent variables. The stakeholders' management is an independent variable. The Pearson correlation of the independent variable (stakeholders' management) with the independent variable is 1 (neutral). However, the Pearson correlation of the independent variable

(stakeholders' management) with the dependent variable (organizational performance) is 0.441. The correlation between 0.3 to 0.5 is considered average. Hence, the 0.441 statistics show the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is an average correlation.

4.4 Model Summary:

In the model summary, the significant figure that leads to an analysis of variables is R square. The R square tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. Similarly, the independent varies the dependent variable at which rate.

Table 4.4.1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate	Change Statistics		
					R Square Change	F Change	df1
1	.441 ^a	.195	.184	.40042	.195	17.431	1

As specified above, the R square defines the variation in the dependent variable caused by the independent variable. The R square change is .195; this depicts that the independent variable (Stakeholders' management) changes the organizational performance by 19%. A variation above 15% is considered significant and acceptable.

Table 4.4.2: Model Summary Change

Model	Change Statistics	
	df2	Sig. F Change
1	72	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Stakeholders Management

The stakeholders' management is constant in the model summary in relation to the dependent variable- organizational performance.

4.5 ANOVA:

The ANOVA tells us the significance of real value. The acceptable figure of ANOVA in quantitative research is 0.05. The ANOVA significance rate for this data analysis study is 0.000; this figure depicts that the ANOVA significance for this study is model fit.

Table 4.5.1: ANOVA a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.795	1	2.795	17.431	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.544	72	.160		
	Total	14.339	73			

4.6. Coefficients

Table 4.6.1: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.917	.219		4.189	.000
	Stakeholders Management	.492	.118	.441	4.175	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

b. Independent Variable: Stakeholders Management

The B value tells us the change in variables. The B value defines the level of change that occurs in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. If we change one unit in the independent variable, the B value depicts that there will be a change of 0.917. Hence, the change of 1 unit in stakeholders' management will result in a change of 0.917 in organizational performance. A T value greater than 1.65 is considered reliable and acceptable in quantitative research. The T value of this study is 4.1; hence it is reliable for dependent and independent variables.

4.7 Factor Analysis:

Table 4.7.1: Correlation Matrix

		Stakeholders Management	Organizational Performance
Correlation	Stakeholders Management	1.000	.441
	Organizational Performance	.441	1.000

The correlation matrix is similar to correlation significance statistics. The change in one variable affects at what level another variable. The correlation of the independent variable (stakeholders' management) with the independent variable itself is 1 (neutral). However, the Pearson correlation of the independent variable (stakeholders' management) with the dependent variable (organizational performance) is 0.441. The correlation between 0.3 to 0.5 is considered average. Hence, the 0.441 statistics show the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is an average correlation.

Table 4.7.2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.500
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	15.501
	Df	1
	Sig.	.000

Table 4.7.3: Component Matrix B

	Component
	1
Stakeholders Management	.849
Organizational Performance	.849

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis A

- a. 1 component extracted.

Table 4.7.4: Communalities

	Extraction
Stakeholders Management	.721
Organizational Performance	.721

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4.8.5: Total Variance Explained

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.441	72.074	72.074

4.8 Reliability:

The reliability elaborates on the validity of questionnaires and questions asked to participants. The measure of questions and their relationship with the responses is depicted in this section.

Table 4.8.1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.710	2

Cronbach's Alpha also depicts the reliability and validity of data analysis based on questionnaires. The Cronbach's Alpha rate also depicts the measurement of variables in the research study. The minimum significant value is 0.5; hence the Cronbach's Alpha rate of this research study is 0.710, which means the variables of this study are measured reliably in questionnaire responses.

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction:

The study was about organizational performance and the factors contributing to the impact of the performance of Bank Dhofar. Stakeholder management is considered the core factor of change in organizational performance. Hence, the research paper aimed to reveal and analyze the relationship between stakeholders' management and the organizational performance of Bank Dhofar. This last chapter of the research study includes the summary of findings generated using statistical software and participants' input collected through questionnaire circulation.

5.2. Summary of findings:

The questionnaire aimed to collect participants' responses on stakeholders' management and organizational performance. The stakeholders' management is considered an independent variable, and organizational performance is the dependent variable, as specified in the chart below:

The independent variable's (stakeholders' management) impacts on the dependent variable (organizational performance) were evaluated through the following components of the questionnaire:

- Stakeholder management and its relationship with organizational performance
- The impacts of stakeholder management on organizational performance in Bank Dhofar
- Stakeholder management process
- Challenges of stakeholder management

The first 4 tables, 4.1.1 to 4.2.3, explain that out of 74 respondents, 45 respondents are male and 29 female and 100 valid, 41 are between the age bracket of 31-40, and 33 are 41-50, 36% diploma, 34% undergraduates, 5% are certificate, and 24% are masters qualified.

1. Stakeholder's management and its relationship with organizational performance:

A- Correlation and significance of correlation:

The significance of correlation depicts the level of relationship between dependent and independent variables. The stakeholders' management is an independent variable. The Pearson correlation of the independent variable (stakeholders' management) with the dependent variable (organizational performance) is 0.441. The correlation between 0.3 to 0.5 is considered average. Table 4.4.1 of correlation specifies the correlation rate of the dependent variable (organizational performance) is 0.441.

2. The impacts of stakeholder management on organizational performance in Bank Dhofar:

A- ANOVA and model summary:

In the model summary, the significant figure that leads to an analysis of variables is R square. The R square tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. Similarly, the independent varies the dependent variable at which rate.

3. Stakeholders' management:

The valid percentile is 74; the rate tells us about the validity of the questionnaire and questions asked by participants. Hence, the researchers can rely on the study and its questionnaires because of high-reliability statistics. Cronbach's Alpha also depicts the reliability and validity of data analysis based on questionnaires. The Cronbach's Alpha rate also depicts the measurement of variables in the research study. The minimum significant value is 0.5; hence the Cronbach's Alpha rate of this research study is 0.710, which means the variables of this study are measured reliably in questionnaire responses.

5.3. Conclusion:

As discussed above in chapter 4, statistical data and summary findings of chapter 5, the results depict that there is a positive and significant relationship between stakeholders' management and the organizational performance of Bank Dhofar. Although the previous studies have not been conducted explicitly focusing on stakeholders' management and its components; however, this study is in line with the various Oman-based studies where one element of change in

organizational performance was stakeholders' management. There is a dire need for Bank Dhofar to manage its stakeholders. As described in chapter one, the stakeholders are clients, investors, employees, central bank employees, and associates related to authoritative institutions such as CPA, legislative bodies, etc., of the Sultanate of Oman. The Pearson correlation of the independent variable (stakeholders' management) with the dependent variable (organizational performance) is 0.441.

5.4. Recommendations

Based on the results of the field study, the literature of relevant peer-reviewed articles, and the findings of previous studies related to stakeholders' management and organizational performance, the researcher recommends a set of mechanisms and procedures to enhance the organizational growth by managing its stakeholders at Bank Dhofar:

- Develop a plan to enhance employees' input in organizational decision-making. Bank Dhofar can help onboard its employees and their input through various methods such as the inauguration of performance evaluation programs, circulating questionnaires, or developing a direct communication mechanism with executive members of the organization.
- Allow and enhance the cooperation with the state's financial and legislation institutions by following the central bank or capital market guidelines and giving the Bank's input in financial decisions of the banking sector.
- The creation of a practical, diverse, competitive, and innovative environment for stakeholders
- Raise the efficiency of stakeholders' management through organizational workshops, training, and seminars
- Choose the best competencies that undertake the stakeholders' management process
- Analyze the current stakeholders' management policies in light of Bank Dhofar's goals

5.5. Limitations:

The research faced some challenges that are listed below:

- The reach to officials and executive board members of Bank Dhofar could not become possible due to a lack of sources for contacts and restrictions by the Bank's information department due to legality issues
- The officials of the Central Bank of Oman and Capital Market did not respond. They were the key stakeholders that legally defined the Bank's status and performance in the banking sector

5.6. Future research:

In the end, the researcher sets some proposed research topics that future researchers can address:

- The categorization of stakeholders and the significant value of stakeholders amongst each other in the eye of financial institutions
- A vision to enhance the stakeholders' management in the banking sector of the Sultanate of Oman

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First, I would like to express my thanks and gratitude to Mr. Festus Odhigu for his guidance and assistance in completing the project in the perfect way and his keenness to provide the best for the students. He also assisted me in improving my analytical skills and supported me from the start to finish, directing and alerting me on all the important aspects of the graduation project, I thank him for motivating me and allocating time to help and review my work.

Secondly, I would like to extend my thanks to all the organizers and teachers for the weekly educational workshops, which were useful for the project points and the way they work in the correct way, and for helping us understand these points and for their responses whenever I have any queries.

My greatest thanks to Bank Dhofar where I work for their approval and support to use the bank's information and to conduct the interviews in order to have this project completed. I would also like to extend my gratitude and thanks to HR Department and Branches Section who were very supported to me especially on distributing the questionnaire and publishing it to the bank's employees. I would also like to extend my thanks to every employee who answered the questionnaire and gave their response with sincerity and appreciation.

At the end, I will never forget the kind support of my family members for encouraging and motivating me throughout my studies, as well as for creating an environment in which I could study and do my best on my graduation project, I will be eternally grateful to them. I would also like to thank my college friends for their full support and for standing together in difficult times of study, discussing, and helping each other to achieve success

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